

Library Automation by Using Newgenlib Open Source Software : A Case Study of Syed Hamid Library(Central Library) in Maulana Azad National Urdu University(Manuu)

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ABSTRACT

Academic Libraries have accepted this challenge and started automation process, in spite of all constraints at their end. This paper describes the various useful service given by NewGenlib library automation software in Syed Hamid Library(Central Library) Maulana Azad National Urdu University(MANUU). It consists of collection of Books, Serials, Manuscript, Bound Volumes, Thesis and Dissertation. User can access catalogue of internet thorough the OPAC. In this paper how the automation process stated in Syed Hamid Library (MANUU) and also knows study how to use open source software (NewGenlib) in MANUU Syed Hamid Central Library. At the same time it also focuses on problems of using on open source (OSS) software in libraries.

KEYWORDS

OSS, OPAC, MANUU.

1. Introduction:

Academic libraries are considered as an important component of any academic institutions. Before 1980 libraries usually used a card catalogue to index their holdings. Now days every major library contains computer for library automation. Computers came into use to automate the card catalogue, this term automation system. After 1980 computer open up separate applications, library staff could now use a single application with multiple functional modules.

They are regarded as the heart of should of the academic setup where all the activities are revolving. Academic library plays an important role in providing overall library and information services to the students. We have just entered in new millennium and we have lot of challenges before us for keeping us in pace with modern development in information technology.

These days' library activities are computerized because of the increasing size and different material in the library. The library which uses computers for housekeeping and information retrieval is called an "automated library".

Maulana Azad National Urdu University (MANUU) Syed Hamid(Central Library) collection and offering reference and information services of their respective community of users. This paper deals MANUU Syed Hamid Library are facing problems in their daily transactions. This paper has been developed in order to overcome the problems and give suggestion to improve the system.

Hence these paper looks into both the benefits and problems associated with the usage of NewGenlib Open Source Software in Syed Hamid Library, MANUU and also locate solutions to the problems faced in implementing such tools.

2. Open Source Software:

The term "Open Source" refers to software in which the source code is freely available for others to view, amend and

adopt. It is created and maintained by a team of developers that crosses institutional and national boundaries. Open source is generally more stable than proprietary software. After all, any programmer can read, distribute and modify source code. It is any explicit "feature" of open source that it may put no restrictions on the use or distribution by any organization or user.

2.1 Use of Open Software:

In order to use Open Source Software in a library, it is essential to first ascertain the requirements of library, availability of manpower and technology aids and also the budget for library activities expansion other than the management inclination towards such an effort.

In current scenario, there are number of open source software applications available for library and information management and hence organizations/libraries have a new option for acquiring and implementing open source systems instead of going in for proprietary products.

2.2 Benefits of using Open Source Software:

Librarians/Professionals are now considering OSS because of its low purchase costs. There is no initial purchase fees, or upgrade fees. A user can access form anywhere, any time provided he has access to the necessary infrastructure. Information can be shared more easily. Open source software it is possible to incorporate the software into another program to perform new function.

2.3 Loss of Using open source Software:

OSS also faces many risks. Especially for long term use which in any case of prime concern for any library OSS has great risk. Given below are some of the risk factors involved which open source software use.

1. No Guarantee of Continuity
2. No Guarantee of updates
3. Unavailability of physical support for installation and trou-

- bleshooting.
- 4. Need of Additional OS/Software
- 5. Lack of Full Features etc.

3. Maulana Azad National Urdu University (MANUU), Hyderabad:

Maulana Azad National Urdu University (MANUU) is a Central University established in 1998 by an Act of Parliament. It is mandated to promote and develop the Urdu language and to impart vocational and technical education in Urdu medium through conventional and distance modes. The headquarters of the university is at an outstanding central location Gachibowli, Hyderabad, sprawling over 200 acres. The University is awarded "A" Grade by National Assessment & Accreditation Council (NAAC) in the year 2009.

3.1 About the Central Library:

The Central Library MANUU main campus is fully automated modernized and connected the network of the university with wireless network facility. The library uses Bar Code, Automation software used as NewGenlib, 3M Tattled Tape Technology Security gate, Tech Focus Software for digitalization and CCTV for monitoring. The library has seating capacity of 200 students and an auditorium with 150 seating capacity.

The library has 53,819 books, 1088 Bound Volumes, 177 Dissertation and 14 Theses. The Library subscribes 159 journals (Print & Soft Copy), popular Magazines, and 13 Newspapers. The library has been extended Jstor, Springer Link, EPW, JCCC@UGC Info net, ISID by the INFLIBNET under UGC Info net Programme. The University staff, researchers and students can directly access the research journals through the server. It has CD/DVD Mirror Software, by which Encyclopedias, Directories, Hand books, etc., can be stored on the Server, and can be accessed on all the nodes on Intranet on the Campus.

4. NewGenlib Software Automaton:

NewGenlib is an integrated library management system developed by Verus Solutions Pvt. Ltd. Domain expertise is provided by Kesavan Institute of Information and Knowledge Management in Hyderabad, India. NewGenlib version 1.0 was release in March 2005. On 9th January 2008 NewGenlib was declared Open Source Software. The latest version of NewGenlib is 3.0.4 release on 4th March 2013.

4.1 NewGenlib Software used in Syed Hamid Library, MANUU:

MANUU Library has shifted SOUL to web-enabled user friendly 'NewGenLib' Library Software which is based on Unicode, by which documents data can be entered and accessed in Urdu, Arabic, Persian, Hindi and all regional languages. The Software is based on Linux, which does not have virus effect.

4.2 Syed Haimd LibraryNewGenlib Server

4.2.1(HP ProLiant ML350 Generation 6) Server:

4.2.1 Hardware Features:

[HP ProLiant ML350 Generation 6](#) (G6)

Chipset Intel® 5520 Chipset, **Processor(s)** (1) Intel® Xeon® Processor E5506 (2.13 GHz, 80 W, DDR3-800), Memory 2 GB

Processor(s) (1) Intel® Xeon® Processor E5620 (2.40 GHz, 80W, DDR3-1066, HT, Turbo

Cache Memory 4MB Level 3 cache
Memory 2 GB (2Rx8 PC3-10600R-9)

Network Controller Embedded NC326i PCI Express Dual Port Gigabit Server Adapter

Storage Controller Smart Array P410i/ZM Controller (RAID 0/1/1+0)

Hard Drive 500 G.B

Internal Storage Up to 6 LFF standard

Optical Drive HP Half-Height SATA DVD-RW Drive

PCI-Express Slots Six expansion slots (six PCI-Express Gen2)

Power Supply (1) HP 460W CS HE Power Supply

Fans 3 included standard, up to 4 total fans supported

Form Factor Tower (5U)

S-Buy ML350TG6 E5620

4.2.2 Software Features:

Windows XP Service pack 2 Operating System we are using in Syed Hamid Library(Central Library), MANUU.

4.3 Modules & Functions:

<p>4.3.1 NewGenLib Main modules: Acquisitions Technical Processing Serials management Circulation</p>	<p>Administration MIS Reports Task to do today (daily scheduler) OPAC</p>
<p>4.3.2.NewGenlib Features:</p>	

<p>a) Functional modules are completely web based. Uses Java Web Start™ Technology</p> <p>b) Compatibility - Complies with international metadata and interoperability standards: MARC-21, MARC-XML, z39.50, SRU/W, OAI-PMH</p> <p>c) Uses chiefly open source components</p> <p>d) Scalable, manageable and efficient</p> <p>e) OS independent - Windows and Linux flavours available</p> <p>f) z39.50 Client for federated searching</p> <p>g) Internationalized application (I18N)</p> <p>h) Unicode 4.0 complaint</p> <p>i) Easily extensible to support other languages</p> <p>j) Data entry, storage, retrieval in any (Unicode 3.0) language</p>	<p>k) RFID integration</p> <p>l) Networking – Hierarchical and Distributed networks</p> <p>m) Automated email/instant messaging integrated into different functions of the software</p> <p>n) Form letters are configurable and use XML-based Open Office templates</p> <p>Extensive use of set up parameters enabling easy configuration of the software to suit specific needs, e.g., in defining patron privileges</p> <p>o) Supports multi-user and multiple security levels</p> <p>p) Allows digital attachments to metadata</p>
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5. MANUU Syed Hamid Library(Central Library) OPAC:

MANUU Library OPAC using NewGenlib software through this it is providing Web-OPAC from its webpage where users can access live database 9.30A.M to 6 P.M. They can also check their circulation status and also reserve the item through the webpage mentioned below by entering their Unique ID and Password. MANUU Central Library provide OPAC with the help of internet the following URL Address <http://172.16.1.3:8080/newgenlibtxt/>

6. Conclusion:

In Open Source Software, It is possible to create a platform for open access. A number of non-profit organizations have released open source library management systems. Open Source Software will be better supported and more easily maintained. Open Source Software's are used for functioning the library.

Open source software is encouraging in a country like India. A number of workshops and training events were organized in India, where a libraries and computer professional received training in open source software for building open access repositories

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